

MANUFACTURING AND TESTING OF AN HYBRID COMPOSITE INTEGRATING VISCOELASTIC FIBERS

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SUMMARY

The requirement of damping treatments in composite structures lead to the need of multifunctional composites designed for dynamic applications. A novel hybrid lamina micro-architecture is proposed where the orthotropic behaviour of viscoelastic fiber is used to increase damping performance of the composite. Unidirectional hybrid composites at two different damping material content were manufactured and tested.

Keywords: hybrid composites, epoxy, carbon fiber, viscoelastic, damping, embedded

INTRODUCTION

Advanced fiber-reinforced plastic composites thanks to their high specific strength and high modulus are increasingly being used in weight sensitive applications. However, the strong depression in structural damping requires the use of damping treatments, conventional damping treatments are based on the addition of a viscoelastic materials [1] that increase energy dissipation in the structure. Structural integrity issues associated with integration into composite material of damping feature presents significant challenges. A possible solution is to integrate damping material as film in the laminate [2] unfortunately this architecture strongly influences not only the failure mechanism, due to the increased magnitude of interlaminar shear stresses at the viscoelastic material/carbon lamina interface, but also the manufacturing process. Developing viscoelastic-damping materials that behave orthotropically [3] is possible to tailor the stiffness and damping properties within the laminate to increase material passive damping.

In this work a novel architecture of the preform is proposed and manufactured where damping material is integrated in lamina as fibres. Unidirectional composite plates of hybrid lamina are manufactured at two different damping material volume fraction and tested by Dynamical mechanical analyzer (DMA).

CONCEPT OF THE HYBRID LAMINA

An innovative viscoelastic fibers hybridised carbon fibers lamina has been conceptualized that integrated viscoelastic fibers between the carbon fiber tows as shown in the figure 1. Such configuration would overcome the problem of integrating in

a composite damped laminate the viscoelastic damping layer that introduces a relevant interlaminar sollicitation at the boundary between the soft damping layer and the high modulus carbon fiber lamina. In addition, such hybrid preform should be manufactured as the conventional ones and used in the dry form for standard liquid resin infiltration processes or in the common preimpregnation systems.

Fig.1 Concept of viscoelastic fibers hybridised carbon fibers lamina

HYBRID SPECIMEN FABBRICATION

Manufacturing of hybrid dry preform

A standard loom has been used to produce the dry viscoelastic fibers hybridised preform from HR 12K, Hexcel carbon fibers tows and Lycra, Du Pont viscoelastic fibers. Viscoelastic Lycra fibers have been positioned along the carbon fibers to have 5% and 10% in volume of the final preform. The figure 2 shows the relevant phases of the hybrid preform manufacturing, i.e. the viscoelastic bobbin (fig.2a), the carbon tows cantra (fig.2b), the ingress of the fibers into the loom (fig.2c), the hybrid preform exit (fig.2d).

Fig.2 Manufacturing of hybrid dry preform.

Manufacturing of hybrid laminate.

Hybrid carbon fiber preform with previously integrated viscoelastic fibers at two volume fraction percentage (5%, 10%) have been used to manufacture laminate by using the RTM6, Hexcel epoxy resin. Composite plates have been manufactured by vacuum infusion process. The figure 3 shows the relevant steps in hybrid flat panel manufacturing. The fig.3a shows the stacking of the hybrid laminae upon the tool,

vacuum bag preparation has been documented in fig 3b, fig 3c shows the infusion process, then the fig.3d shows the curing of the laminate followed by the demolding phase (fig.3e). As produced coupon is shown in the fig.3f . The specimens were cutted from plates along and orthogonally the fibres direction. An additional plate without fibres were manufactured as baseline in tests.

Fig.3 Hybrid composite manufacturing via Vacuum Infusion Process

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Micrograph in fig.4 shows the lamina constituent distribution in the case of 5% specimen: matrix, carbon fibers and a single Lycra fiber. The viscoelastic fiber has not be integrated within the carbon fiber tow but has been positioned within the inter tow spacing.

Fig.4 Micrograph of the section of the 5% specimen.

Dynamic measurement were carried out using TA DMTA 2980 in three point bending testing mode, with 50 mm span between the supports. The temperature scan measurements were performed over the temperature range of -50°C to 180°C with

heating rate of 5.0 °C/min and constant frequency of 1.0 Hz. In table 1 are reported data at -30°C, where verification of the damping performance is required by the aeronautical application. The 5% hybrid preform performed a negligible effect in fiber direction, but in transverse direction a 20% increment has obtained over the decreasing in transverse elastic modulus. The 10% hybrid preform had a strong decrease in material stiffness.

Table 1: Measured elastic moduli and $\tan\delta$ in both direction

@-30°C	v_f	E_1 (GPa)	$\tan\delta$	E_2 (GPa)	$\tan\delta$
CFRC	0	132.13	0.00719	12.77	0.0167
5% hybrid	0.02	132.09	0.00754	10.48	0.0203
10% hybrid	0.05	82.53	0.0131	8.29	0.0261
neat Lycra	1	0.113	0.292	0.113	0.292

CONCLUSIONS

An hybrid composite material based on a novel lamina architecture that integrates viscoelastic fibers along structural carbon fibers has been proposed, manufactured and preliminary tested. Such architecture should control the magnitude of interlaminar shear stresses experienced in the interleaved configuration actually used in high damping applications. Unidirectional eight plies hybrid laminate has been manufactured via Vacuum Assisted Liquid Molding and mechanically tested to measure the bending moduli and the loss in both principal directions. At the temperature of -30° C that corresponds to the operative temperature in aeronautical applications an increment of the damping capacity in the orthogonal to fiber directions of 60% has been reached in the case of 10% specimen. In the case of 5% specimen the increase of the loss capacity is 20% and in the latter case the bending modulus in 0° direction has been kept to the reference value. Results encourages the further development of the proposed architecture, especially in manufacturing hybrid preforms where viscoelastic fibers should be included within the carbon tows.

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